

ANALYZING BANK-SPECIFIC PERFORMANCE METRICS, STABILITY AND CAPITAL ADEQUACY: A STUDY OF SELECTED LISTED DEPOSIT MONEY BANKS IN NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

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This study analyzed how capital adequacy affects the stability of eight quoted banks in Nigeria from 2010 to 2023. Using secondary data and a Panel Autoregressive Distributed Lag (PARDL) model, it examined four key variables: bank capital to total credit ratio (BCTCA), loan to deposit ratio (LDR), debt to equity ratio (DER), and risk-weighted assets (RWA). Findings revealed that LDR and DER negatively impact bank stability, while BCTCA and RWA have positive effects. The study recommends that Nigerian banks enhance stability by reducing LDR and DER, and increasing BCTCA and RWA

1.0 INTRODUCTION

The banking sector plays a pivotal role in the economic development of any nation, serving as a critical intermediary between savers and borrowers and facilitating efficient capital allocation. In Nigeria, Deposit Money Banks (DMBs) are central to the financial system and are instrumental in driving economic growth through credit creation, financial intermediation,

and investment facilitation (Yua, & Temitope 2024). Given their importance, assessing the performance, stability, and capital adequacy of these banks is essential for ensuring systemic resilience and fostering investor confidence

The realization of the importance of the banking sector stability informed the recent decision of the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) on March 28, 2024 to raise the capital requirements for Nigerian commercial, merchant, and non-interest banks. For the commercial banks, it was increased from N25/N50 billion to N200/N500 billion for National and Internal banking operations respectively. In light of the current macroeconomic problems, the CBN believes that the recapitalization exercise is essential for banks to improve their resilience, solvency, and capacity while continuing to support the growth of the Nigerian economy. The initiative is specifically the apex bank's response to the effect of the depreciation of the naira on bank capital and to guarantee that the banking sector has sufficient capital buffer to support the \$1 trillion GDP projected by 2026 and foster financial stability, (CBN 2024).

The bank-specific performance indicators, stability, and capital adequacy is essential for assessing the health and efficiency of banks in Nigeria. These factors collectively contribute to the robustness of the financial system and play a significant role in promoting economic stability and growth (Yua, Epor, & Ajekwe, 2025). In the financial sector, performance indicators serve as essential tools for evaluating the health and efficiency of banks. These indicators are particularly critical in the context of Nigeria, where the banking sector plays a pivotal role in economic development. Bank-specific performance metrics such as profitability, asset quality, and liquidity provide insights into the operational success and resilience of financial institutions (Omale, Yua, & Azubuike, 2024; Oleribe & Taylor-Robinson, 2016).

Bank stability refers to the ability of a banking institution to withstand economic shocks and financial stress without facing insolvency or requiring external assistance (Soomiyol, Bwuese, & Yua, 2023). In Nigeria, the stability of banks is crucial for maintaining the overall health of the financial system. Factors influencing bank stability include capital adequacy, asset quality, management efficiency, and earnings performance. Regulatory frameworks and supervisory practices by the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) also play a significant role in ensuring stability. Research indicates that macroeconomic stability, effective regulatory oversight, and sound risk management practices are essential for maintaining bank stability in Nigeria (, Yua, Epor, & Utor, 2023; sSanusi, 2010).

Capital adequacy is a critical measure of a bank's financial strength and its ability to absorb losses. It is typically assessed using the Capital Adequacy Ratio (CAR), which compares a bank's capital to its risk-weighted assets. The CBN mandates that Nigerian banks maintain a minimum CAR to ensure they can absorb a reasonable amount of loss and protect depositors' funds. Adequate capitalization is fundamental for enhancing confidence in the banking sector and for the sustainable growth of banks (Ordue, Yua, Ityavyar, & Tarnongo, 2024) Adegbite & Alabi, 2020). The global standards set by the Basel Accords also influence capital adequacy requirements, and Nigerian banks are required to comply with these international benchmarks to enhance their competitiveness and stability.

The findings of earlier research revealed divergence views among researchers about the relationship between capital and stability. While studies by Salami & Uthman (2018) and Oyetayo et al. (2019) suggested that capital regulation and bank stability had a positive relationship; studies by Igbinsa & Naimo (2020); Okoi et al. (2019); and Obilikwu (2018) reported a negative (or negligible) relationship. It is evident that earlier research has mixed results. Concerns are currently being raised about whether a robust capital base, as advocated

by the CBN, will automatically stabilize the banking sector because prior research seems to be mired in empirical dispute. Furthermore, published research indicates that a deluge of previous studies has focused on the financial performance (mostly profitability) of banks, even though regulatory bodies place the highest priority on bank stability. In light of this, this study examined the bank-specific performance metrics, bank stability and capital adequacy: A Study of selected listed deposit money banks in Nigeria.

2 Literature Review

2.1 Theoretical Review.

The Buffer Theory of Capital Adequacy

The buffer theory of Calmed and Rob (1996) predicts that a bank approaching the regulatory minimum capital ratio may have an incentive to boost capital and reduce risk in order to avoid the regulatory costs triggered by a breach of the capital requirements. The theory posits that whenever a bank's capital is marginally above the regulatory minimum ratio, there is a need for the bank to increase the ratio in order to minimize risk and avoid the regulatory cost as a result of a breach of the capital requirements (Ajayi et. al., 2019). Capital adequacy empowers banks to diversify their portfolio in order to mitigate risks and ensure stability (Aroghene & Ikeora, 2022). Low level of capital increases the chances of bank failure while sufficient and adequate capital lead to improved financing activities hence impacting positively on the value of the bank. Igbinosa and Naimo (2020) availed that whenever banks hold adequate capital it forms a basis for trust from shareholders. Highly capitalized-banks confidently embark on risky but high return investments leading to increased value. The assumption of this theory is that capital is one element that determines the level of financial risks that banks can contain in their operations.

This study is underpinned by the buffer theory which postulates that banks may prefer to hold a “buffer” of excess capital to reduce the probability of falling under the legal capital requirements, especially if their capital adequacy ratio is very volatile. The buffer theory predicts that a bank approaching the regulatory minimum capital ratio may have an incentive to boost capital and reduce risk to avoid the regulatory costs triggered by a breach of the capital requirements. However, poorly capitalized banks may also be tempted to take more risk in the hope that higher expected returns will help them to increase their capital. This is one of the ways risks relating to lower capital adequacy affects banking operations. In the event of bankruptcy of a bank, the risks are absorbed by the bank and Insurance Corporation (NDIC).

Banks in Nigeria hold excess capital buffers to reduce risk of falling under legal capital requirements, especially if their capital adequacy ratio is volatile. The Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) conducts on-site examinations and delegates this task to external auditors. Banks require more capital if deposits aren't fully mobilized, as it's more reliable and can be used for long-term planning. Poorly capitalized banks take risks to increase capital, affecting banking operations.

2.3 Empirical Review

Previous attempts made to empirically evaluate how capital adequacy requirement drives banks' performance indicators.

Ezu, Nwanna, & Eke-Jeff (2023). Evaluates capital adequacy on the performance of Nigerian deposit money banks for the period of 2000 – 2020. The objective of this study is to examine how capital adequacy has helped deposit moneybanks achieve an efficient

performance. This study adopts an ex-post facto research design, and the sample size is all deposit money banks with international and national authorization in Nigeria. The data used are mainly secondary data collected from the audited annual publications financial statements of all the deposit money banks listed on the Nigerian Stock Exchange. The study employed ordinary least square multiple regression (OLS), descriptive statistical analysis, in addition to E-view electronic packages. According to empirical results at 5% level of significance, findings show that total capital to risk weighted assets, banks capitalization to total credits, and debt to equity ratio (the independent variables to capital adequacy) had direct and inverse linear significant effect on return on assets (dependent variable to performance) of deposit money banks in Nigeria. The study concludes that capital adequacy, one of the key factors affecting the performance of the Nigeria deposit money banks in measuring efficient performance of financial institutions in Nigeria has both direct and inverse linear relationship with efficient performance of banks, therefore, recommends that the Central Bank of Nigeria should effectively regulate the capital and the resources owned by the deposit money banks (DMBs) in Nigeria to globally acceptable standard since the current ₦25 billion and ₦50 billion minimum capital-base requirements cannot justify the banking reality of nowadays. This will help to enhance investment planning, decision making within the financial system and early prevention of systemic bank distress.

Nenubari, Joseph, John & Linus (2022). examined bank-specific performance indicators and macroeconomic factors affecting the short-term financing obligation of Nigerian banks from 2010 to 2019. The data for the study are sourced annually from the financial statements of the selected Deposit Money Banks and the Central Bank of Nigeria Statistical Bulletin. The panel unit root and co-integration tests are employed to ascertain the sustainability of the bank-specific performance indicators. The models for the industry were cast in a host of panel frameworks such that we estimated the static and dynamic panel models. The study observed that the capital adequacy ratio, which is the short-term financing obligation of Nigerian banks was elastic to bank profitability positively. In addition, interbank call rate, bank size, and oil price positively influence the capital adequacy ratio over time, whereas loan-to-deposit ratio, inflation and exchange rate exacerbate the capital adequacy ratio. Consequently, we canvass that Nigerian banks should reduce dividend payouts and increase retained profits as a buffer against exposed risks.

Akinroluyo & Adeoti (2022). investigated capital adequacy and Deposit Money Bank's (DMB) Return on Asset (ROA) in Nigeria in which the effect of capital to asset ratio on bank's profit margin and the relationship between solvency and asset turnover was examined. The study population of the study comprised Nigeria deposit money banks listed on the floor of Nigeria Stock Exchange as at 2021. Sample of bank selected was Zenith Plc, Guaranty Trust Bank Plc (GTB), First Bank Nigeria Limited, Access Bank Plc, and United Bank for Africa Plc based on global ranking order and the fact that they are listed on Nigeria Stock Exchange. To determine the effect of capital adequacy on banks performance, Ordinary Least Square (OLS) regression model was employed the data collected within the period of 2006-2020. The findings of this study revealed coefficient of 0.080034 implies 1% change in capital to asset ratio would lead to 8% increase change in profit margin ratio and p-value of 0.042223 shows that CTA has statistical significant effect on profit margin of the selected banks within the period under study; coefficient of 0.04587 implies 1% change in solvency would lead to 4.58% change in asset turnover of the selected DMBs under the period studied, p-value of 0.0000611 shows that SOLV has statistical significant relationship with ATU of the selected banks within the period under study. The study recommends bank decision makers should give consideration for its solvency status and capital to asset ratio when investigating factors affecting bank's actualization objective. In addition, DMBs in Nigeria should ensure that they maintain above minimum capital to asset ratio level in order to

guarantee an efficient profit margin. Also, the ability of DMBs to meet their short and medium term financial obligations must be fortified in order to keep the performance at per.

3. Data and Methodology

Model Specification

To derive a model specification for the relationship between capital adequacy and bank stability, the study adopt the model of (Oke & Ikpesu, 2022; Ogunode et al., 2022; Aroghene & Ikeora, 2022; Ajayi et al., 2019; Aliu et al., 2020; Aliyu et al., 2020) which the model for the study is specified thus:

$$BST = f(BCTCA, LDR, DER, RWA)$$

Where,

BST	- bank stability
BCTCA	- bank capitalization to total credit assets ratio
LDR	- loan to deposit ratio
DER	- debt-to-equity ratio
RWA	- risk-weighted assets

Technique for Data Analysis

Econometric approach is adopted in this study to analyze collected time-series cross-sectional data. Econometrically, statistical, economical and mathematical techniques will be applied to analyze the longitudinal data so as to validate the formulated hypotheses. Statistically, descriptive and inferential techniques are employed. By these, it means data is first subjected to descriptive statistics check followed by inferential statistics.

The inferential statistics covers different tests, starting with unit-root test (to ascertain data stationarity properties), the co-integration test (to ascertain the variables' long-run relationship) and the panel data estimation technique (Panel Autoregressive Distributed Lag, PARDL).

Once cointegration is established between capital adequacy and bank stability, the conditional P-ARDL long-run model can be specified as:

$$BST_t = \omega_0 + \omega_1 BCTCA_{t-i} + \omega_2 LDR_{t-i} + \omega_3 DER_{t-i} + \omega_4 RWA_{t-i} + \epsilon_t$$

Where,

ω_0	=	intercept
$\omega_1-\omega_5$	=	coefficients of long-run estimates
ϵ_t	=	error term of long-run estimates

In the next step, we obtain the short-run dynamic parameters by estimating an error correction model associated with the long-run estimates. This is specified as follows:

$$\Delta BST_t = \alpha_0 + \sum_{i=1}^a \beta_i \Delta BST_{t-i} + \sum_j^b \gamma_j \Delta BCTCA_{t-j} + \sum_k^c \delta_k \Delta LDR_{t-k} + \sum_l^d \theta_l \Delta DER_{t-l} + \sum_m^e \vartheta_m \Delta RWA_{t-m} + \phi ECT_{t-1} + \mu_t$$

Where,

ECT = error correction term derived from equation (3.7), and

ϕ = the speed of adjustment.

The error correction model shows the speed of adjustment needed to restore the long run equilibrium following a short run shock. The ϕ is the coefficient of the error correction term in the model and must be negative and significant for the return back to long-run equilibrium to hold.

4. Analysis and Results

Table 1 provides summary data for the study's variables. Several problems are revealed by closely examining the descriptive statistics for the dependent and explanatory variables. It is preferable to reiterate the concepts of bank stability and capital adequacy for the sake of emphasis. The z-score of banks defines the dependent variable, bank stability (BST). The loan to deposit ratio (LDR), debt to equity ratio (DER), risk-weighted average asset (RWA), and capitalization to total loan ratio (BCTCA) are among the independent factors. The percentages are used to express each variable.

Table 4.1: Descriptive Statistics for Dependent and Explanatory Variables

	BST (%)	BCTCA (%)	DER (%)	LDR (%)	RWA (%)
Mean	4.348	39.179	67.902	65.721	118.377
Median	1.190	26.930	63.310	61.810	58.820
Maximum	85.030	292.090	252.190	218.530	949.290
Minimum	0.030	10.300	0.080	24.270	22.970
Std. Dev	10.960	48.018	51.529	23.961	202.227
Skewness	5.354	3.973	0.849	2.657	3.050
Kurtosis	35.170	18.349	3.630	17.801	10.726
Observations	101	101	101	101	101

Source: Researcher's Computation using EViews

A cursory examination of the bank stability metrics reveals an average of 4.35, with maximum and minimum values of 85.03 and 1.19. The weight of bank capital against total loans is just 39.18%, or more than twice the value of equity capital, according to the mean value of 39.179 for the bank capitalization to loan ratio. The range of 292.09% to 26.93% indicates that, on average, loan assets exceeded equity capital, although there are unusual occasions where capital exceeds total loans. The debt-to-equity ratio's mean of 67.90%

indicates that banks used less borrowed capital than equity capital. The fact that the DER values vary from 63.31% to 252.19% indicates that there have been times when the use of debt has outpaced the use of equity. With an average ratio of 65.72%, loans to deposit values indicate that loans were smaller than deposit values. This implies that deposit money were distributed among non-credit assets as well, lowering the degree of exposure to credit risk.

However, the results showed that the risk-weighted assets were more prone to swings than any other variable considered in this study. This is seen by the 202.2267 standard deviation, which is higher than the capital adequacy indexes and bank stability combined. However, decisions about bank stability were often changed when bank policies changed. This demonstrates how competitive the banking sector is.

Correlation Analysis

To investigate the correlation between variables, the correlation matrix for the variables is provided in Table 4.2 below. The findings indicate that the bank capital to total credit ratio and BST have a negative association. In contrast, risk-weighted assets, the debt-to-equity ratio, and the loan-to-deposit ratio are positively correlated with bank stability. This implies that bank stability and these subsequent variables move in the same way. Only the correlation between risk-weighted assets and bank stability, nevertheless, was found to be statistically significant.

Table 4.2: Correlation Matrix of the Variables

Probability	BST	BCTCA	DER	LDR	RWA
BST	1				
BCTCA	-0.0177	1			
DER	0.0254	-0.3262	1		
LDR	0.0080	-0.3668	0.0461	1	
RWA	0.2540	-0.1288	-0.1344	0.4082	1

Source: Researcher's Computation using EViews

To identify potential cases of multicollinearity or strong linear relationships, we will examine the correlational relationship among the independent variables from two different angles: (i) direction, (ii) significance, and (iii) strength of association. First, there is a negative correlation between the bank capitalization to loan ratio and risk-weighted assets, loan to equity, and debt to equity. DER and LDR have a positive correlation while DER and RWA have a negative correlation. The loan to deposit ratio and risk-weighted assets showed a positive correlation, to sum up. The statistical analysis revealed that there was a strong negative connection between BCTCA and both LDR and DER. Besides these, the relationship between RWA and LDR was also statistically significant. On the basis of the strength of relationship, none of the linear relationships among the independent variables exceeded 0.4, a level that suggest there is no scare of possible multicollinearity problem. So, the specification order in chapter three is good for estimation.

Panel Unit Root Tests

To determine the order of integration for the variables utilized, we checked for unit root in order to retest the capital adequacy-bank stability hypothesis for the chosen DMBs. Thus, we implemented the unit root test of the Levin, Lin, and Chu (LLC) panel. The variable has unit

root (i.e., an individual unit root process) according to the LLC panel unit root test's null hypothesis.

The p-values for BST, BCTCA, LDR, and DER were not more than 0.05, according to the unit root test results (Table 4.3), which means that the null hypothesis for nonstationarity is rejected at a significance level of 0.05. Thus, it may be said that the debt-to-equity ratio, loan-to-deposit ratio, bank stability, and bank capitalization to total credit ratio are all integrated of order zero, or I(0). RWA, the variable, was differenced and integrated at order I since it was not stationary at levels.

Table 4.3: Panel Unit Root Test

Variable	Levin, Lin & Chu test	Levin, Lin & Chu test at levels		Levin, Lin & Chu test at first difference	
		Statistics	p-values	Statistics	p-values
BST	Levin, Lin & Chu test	-8.74353	0.0000***		
BCTCA	Levin, Lin & Chu test	-2.03935	0.0207**		
DER	Levin, Lin & Chu test	-1.77767	0.0377**		
LDR	Levin, Lin & Chu test	-1.64143	0.0504**		
RWA	Levin, Lin & Chu test	-0.10974	0.4563	-6.97319	0.0000***

Note: *, **, *** are significance at 10%, 5% and 1% respectively

Source: Researcher's Computation using EViews

Given this finding, the variables used in this study are said to be integrated of orders I(0) and I(1). This order of integration enables us to use the autoregressive distributed lags estimation technique (Pesaran et al., 2001). Also with majority of the variables being integrated at order one, I(0), it suggests that there is a high possibility of a long run relationship.

4.2.3 Panel Cointegration Test

The p-values for BST, BCTCA, LDR, and DER were not more than 0.05, according to the unit root test results (Table 4.3), which means that the null hypothesis for nonstationarity is rejected at a significance level of 0.05. Thus, it may be said that the debt-to-equity ratio, loan-to-deposit ratio, bank stability, and bank capitalization to total credit ratio are all integrated of order zero, or I(0). RWA, the variable, was differenced and integrated at order I since it was not stationary at levels.

Table 4.4: Pedroni Residual Cointegration Tests

<i>BST = f(LDR, BCTCA, DER, RWA)</i>				
	Weighted			
	Statistic	Prob.	Statistic	Prob.
Panel v-Statistic	-2.6761	0.9963	-2.5624	0.9948
Panel rho-Statistic	1.009707	0.8437	1.372889	0.9151
Panel PP-Statistic	-13.9337	0.0000***	-12.5206	0.0000***
Panel ADF-Statistic	-2.6134	0.0045***	-3.7177	0.0001***
Group rho-Statistic	2.254512	0.9879		
Group PP-Statistic	-17.16547	0.0000***		
Group ADF-Statistic	-2.196182	0.0140***		

Note: *, **, *** are significance at 10%, 5% and 1% respectively

Source: Researcher's Computation using EViews

We infer that there is a cointegrating relationship among the variables employed since the majority of test statistics (6 out of 11 tests) reject the null hypothesis that there is no cointegration and because the p-value is less than 0.05. We estimated the long run panel ARDL in this study (based on the Pooled Mean Group) based on the findings of the cointegration and unit root tests. It should be mentioned that this is more of an artistic than a scientific decision to use cointegration. The reasoning for this is that, unless the error correction model indicates otherwise, it is prudent to reject the null hypothesis that there is no cointegration if at least one test statistic indicates its presence. Thus, we will now estimate the inaccuracy. If the coefficient of the ECT is negative and statistically significant, we can validate our long run relationship from the Pedrini tests.

Long-run Panel ARDL Model Estimation

The panel ARDL results were estimated from the best model, ARDL (1, 1, 1, 1, 1), selected based on Akaike info criterion (AIC). The estimation below presents the long-run relationship between the capital adequacy indicators and the bank stability of deposit money banks in Nigeria.

The long run model of the panel autoregressive distributed lag (PARDL) method is given as:

$$BST = 0.0083 * BCTCA - 0.0011 * DER - 0.0158 * LDR + 0.0379 * RWA$$

From the model estimation above, the coefficients of bank capitalization to total credit ratio and risk weighted asset were positive to bank stability. This means that as the ratios of bank capital to credit and risk weighted assets increases, bank stability tends to increase, and vice versa. On the other hand, the ratios of debt to equity and loan to deposit have negative effects on bank stability. This means that, the ratios of debt to equity and loan to deposit move in different direction with bank stability.

Short-run and Long-run Panel ARDL and Error Correction Model Estimation

Having established the long-run relationship between the capital adequacy variables and bank stability, this section discusses the short-run results of the study. Thus, table 4.5 illustrates the short-run results of the Error Correction Model, estimated by the PMG estimators which the Panel ARDL is framed on. The short-run results for the four models show a significant and negative error correction term (ECT) of -1.3167. This means that 131.67% of deviations from the long-run equilibrium of bank stability model with the capital adequacy positions of Nigerian banks is restored in a high degree. This high Error Correction Term (ECT) shows that there is a stable relationship between bank stability and capital adequacy among Nigerian banks.

Table 4.5: Short-run Error Correction and Long-run Estimation s

Dependent Variable: D(BST)							
Method: ARDL							
Dynamic regressors (1 lag, automatic): BCTCA DER LDR RWA							
Selected Model: ARDL(1, 1, 1, 1, 1)							
Short Run Equation				Long Run Equation			
Variable	Coefficient	t-Statistic	Prob.*	Variable	Coefficient	t-Statistic	Prob.*
ECT01	-1.3167	-7.1718	0.0000	BCTCA	0.0083	3.0501	0.0037
D(BCTCA)	-0.3738	-0.8609	0.3935	DER	-0.0011	-2.1291	0.0383
D(DER)	-0.0102	-0.2369	0.8137	LDR	-0.0158	-3.4373	0.0012
D(LDR)	0.0177	0.1288	0.8980	RWA	0.0379	10.6704	0.0000
D(RWA)	0.2386	1.2782	0.2072				
C	1.3557	0.7149	0.4780				

Source: Researcher's Computation using EViews

According to the study, from 2010 to 2021, loan to deposit ratios (LDR) and debt to equity ratios (DER) significantly impacted bank stability in Nigerian banks. Since the significance threshold (0.05) is greater than the p-value for LDR (-0.0012), it may be concluded that these ratios have a detrimental impact on bank stability. The fact that the p-value for DER (0.0383) is lower than the significance level (0.05) further suggests that these ratios are detrimental to the stability of banks. As a result, the null hypothesis—which states that there is no discernible effect on bank stability—is rejected, showing that these ratios significantly harm Nigerian banks.

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5. Discussion of findings, Conclusion and Recommendation

Discussion of findings

The first goal was to determine how the loan to deposit ratio affected the stability of banks in Nigeria. Remember that the loan to deposit ratio's p-value in the bank stability model was less than the significance level, leading us to draw the conclusion that the ratio significantly undermines the stability of Nigerian banks. Whatever the amount of loan to deposit ratio, it will push bank stability in the other direction, according to the Panel ARDL long-run estimates, which demonstrate that loan to deposit ratio has a considerable effect on the stability of quoted deposit money banks in Nigeria. This result conflicts with that of Amahalu et al. (2017), who examined the impact of capital adequacy on the performance of 14 listed banks and discovered that capital adequacy (measured by the liquid asset ratio, loan ratio, and asset turnover ratio) significantly improves returns on equity, capital employed, and returns on assets.

The difference in the findings is attributed to the use of different indicators and technique of estimation. Although the findings of this study showed a negative effect from loan to deposit ratio on bank stability, it has however proven that loan to deposit ratio is a significant determinant of bank stability (Ogbebor et al., 2019). Determining the impact of the debt-to-equity ratio on the stability of Nigerian banks was the second goal. We came to the conclusion that the debt-to-equity ratio significantly negatively affects bank stability in Nigeria since the p-value for the ratio in the bank stability model was less than the significance level. According to the Panel ARDL long-run estimations, the debt-to-equity ratio significantly affects the stability of Nigerian listed banks, which means that it significantly undermines the stability of Nigerian banks.

This study primarily implies that banks should reduce their debt-to-equity ratio in order to boost stability. This result is consistent with that of Ogunode et al. (2022), who reported that there was a favorable correlation between company success and the debt-to-equity ratio. The most widely used indicator of bank performance, return on asset, may be used to calculate bank stability. Based on this, we can conclude that one important factor that can improve the overall stability of Nigerian banks is how well debt capital is used in their capital structure.

The study's third objective was aimed to determine the impact of bank capitalization to total credit assets ratio on the stability of Nigerian banks. The results showed that the ratio significantly positively affects the stability of quoted deposit money banks in Nigeria. This suggests that the positive sign of the ratio coefficient should be considered. The main implication is that increasing the ratio in banks' books will increase their stability, and vice versa. This finding agrees with Oke and Ikpesu, (2022) that there is a positive relationship between capital adequacy and asset quality, and the performance of banks in Nigeria. Therefore, it can be inferred that the presence of sufficient capital and high asset quality positively impact and promote the overall performance of the banking sector within the nation. Furthermore, the study's results suggest that sufficient capital and robust asset quality have a positive impact on the profitability and overall effectiveness of banking institutions. On the contrary, this study's findings disagreed with Ogunode et al, (2022) who found that certain financial indicators, such as the capital adequacy ratio, equity capital to total assets ratio, and cost income ratio, had a negative impact on the overall performance of companies listed in Nigeria.

The fourth goal of the study was to determine the impact of risk-weighted assets on the stability of Nigerian banks. The results showed that risk-weighted assets, especially quoted deposit money banks, had a considerable beneficial impact on the stability of Nigerian banks. The risk-weighted asset p-value was less than 0.05, suggesting that commercial banks' bank stability situations improve in tandem with an increase in risk-weighted assets. This implies that better bank stability may result from having more risk-weighted assets. The results of this study are consistent with those of Obadire (2022), who found that there was a statistically insignificant negative correlation between the stability of banks operating in the African region and the minimum capital requirement, capital adequacy ratio, and capital buffer premium. Additionally, there is a small disagreement with Aroghene and Ikeora's (2022) findings about the Capital Adequacy Ratio.

Conclusion

From 2010 to 2022, this study looked at how capital sufficiency affected the stability of Nigeria's listed banks. The bank capital to total credit ratio (BCTCA), risk weighted asset (RWA), debt to equity ratio (DER), and loan to deposit ratio (LDR) were all included in the study as indicators of bank capital adequacy. The z-score of banks (BST) was used as the dependent variable. The study made use of statistical techniques such panel ARDL regression analysis and correlation analysis. In order to better understand the consequences of capital adequacy, it is difficult to ignore the study's examination of several important capital adequacy variables. These factors include risk weighted assets (RWA), debt to equity ratio (DER), loan to deposit ratio (LDR), and bank capital to total credit ratio (BCTCA). Study's findings, it can be concluded that: In Nigeria, the loan to deposit ratio (LDR) and the debt to equity ratio (DER) have a notable negative impact on bank stability, whereas Risk weighted assets (RWA) and the bank capital to total credit ratio (BCTCA) both significantly improve the stability of Nigerian banks.

So, in summary, increasing or reducing the capital adequacy indicators matter to bank stability in Nigeria.

Recommendation

Based on the findings and conclusions, the study proffers the following recommendations:

- i. The study suggests that Nigerian banks should reduce their loan to deposit ratio to improve stability, as more bad loans expose banks to capital losses.
- ii. Research indicates that Nigerian banks' debt to equity ratio significantly affects their stability, suggesting that firms should reduce leverage levels to increase stability.
- iii. The study indicates that a bank's capitalization to total credit ratio significantly impacts its stability, suggesting that banks should increase their capital cover for loan assets.
- iv. The study indicates that a bank's capitalization to total credit ratio significantly impacts its stability, suggesting that banks should increase their capital cover for loan assets.

References

- Adegbite, E. O., & Alabi, F. (2020). Capital Adequacy and Banks' Profitability: An Empirical Study of Banks in Nigeria. *Journal of Finance and Banking Studies*, 9(1), 45-58.
- Ajayi, S. O., Ajayi, H. F., Enimola, D. J., & Orugun, F. I. (2019). Effect of capital adequacy ratio (car) on profitability of deposit money banks (dmb's): a study of dmb's with international operating license in Nigeria. *Research Journal of Finance and Accounting*, 10(10), 84-91.
- Aliu, A.A., Abdullahi, N.A., & Bakare, T.O. (2020). Capital adequacy and financial performance of deposit money banks with international authorization in Nigeria. *Accounting and Taxation Review*, 4(4): 78-91.
- Aliyu, A. A., Abdullyhi, N. A., & Bakare, T. O. (2020). Capital adequacy and financial performance of deposit money banks with international authorization in Nigeria. *Accounting and taxation review*, 4(4), 78-91.
- Amahalu, N., Okoye, E. I., Nweze, C., Chinyere, O., & Christian, O. (2017, July). Effect of capital adequacy on financial performance of quoted deposit money banks in Nigeria. In *Chapter 57 in the proceedings of the 2017 International Conference on African Entrepreneurship and Innovation for Sustainable Development (AEISD)*.
- Aroghene, K. G., & Ikeora, J. J. E. (2022). Effect of non-performing loans (npls), capital adequacy (ca) and corporate governance (cg) on bank stability in Nigeria. *Finance & Accounting Research Journal*, 4(4), 180-192.
- Ezu, G., Nwanna, I. O., & Eke-Jeff, O. M. (2023). Effect of capital adequacy on the performance of deposit money banks in Nigeria. *International Journal of Novel Research in Marketing Management and Economics*, 10(1), 53-63.
- Igbinosa, S. O. & Naimo, F. A. (2020). Capital adequacy and bank stability/soundness in sub-Saharan Africa. *European Journal of Accounting, Finance and Investment*, 6(5), 38-54.
- Laeven, L., & Levine, R. (2009). Bank governance, regulation and risk taking. *Journal of financial economics*, 93(2), 259-275.
- Michael, E. I., Etukafia, N. I., Akpabio, E. E. & Etuk, M. I. (2018). Capital adequacy and the value of banks in Nigeria: a post-consolidation review. *Journal of Finance and Bank Management*, 6(2), 64-75.
- Mishkin, F. S. (1992). *The Economics of money, banking and financial markets* (3 rd ed) (New York: Harper Collins Publishers).
- Nwagbara, C. (2020). CBN may announce new recapitalization plan soon. Nairametrics. Retrieved (07/15/2023) from <https://nairametrics.com/2020/01/13/cbn-may-announce-new-recapitalisation-plan-soon/>.
- Nwankwo, S. N. P. (2019). Effect of capital adequacy on commercial bank's financial performance in Nigeria, 2010-2017. *European Journal of Accounting, Finance and Investment*, 5(4), 1-21.
- Obadire, A. M. (2022). Banking regulation effects on African banks' stability. *Journal of Financial Risk Management*, 11(4), 707-726.

- Obilikwu, J. (2018). The impact of capital, concentration, size and liquidity on banking industry performance in Nigeria. *International Journal of Economics and Financial*, 8(4), 54-60.
- Ofeimun, G. & Akpotor, V. A. (2020). Effect of capital adequacy on banks' performance in Nigeria: 2010 – 2019. *Economics and Social Sciences Academic Journal*, 2(7), 1-9.
- Ogbebor, P. I., Oguntodu, J. A., & Osho, L. A. (2020). Capital adequacy and return on assets of deposit money banks quoted in Nigeria. *International Journal of Management Sciences and Business Research*, 9(2), 111-120.
- Ogunode, O. A., Awoniyi, O. A., & Ajibade, A. T. (2022). Capital adequacy and corporate performance of non-financial firms: Empirical evidence from Nigeria. *Cogent Business & Management*, 9(1), 2156089.
- Oke, B. & Ikpesu, F. (2022). Capital Adequacy, Asset Quality and Banking Sector Performance in Nigeria. *Acta Universitatis Danubius. Œconomica*, 18(5). Retrieved from <https://dj.univ-danubius.ro/index.php/AUDOE/article/view/1843>
- Okoi, I. O., Ocheni, S. I. & Orok, A. B. (2019). Impact of banking sector reforms on economic growth in Nigeria. *European Journal of Scientific Research*, 154(2), 230-240.
- Oleribe, O. O. & Taylor-Robinson, S. D. (2016). Before Sustainable Development Goals (SDG): Why Nigeria Failed to Achieve the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs). *Pan African Medical Journal*, 24, 156.
- Oyetayo, O. J., Osinubi, T. S. & Amaghionyeodiwe, L. (2019). Capital adequacy and banks performance: a case study of selected banks in Nigeria. *International Journal of Economics, Commerce and Management*, VII(9), 63-78.
- Ozili, P. K. (2018). Banking stability determinants in Africa. *International Journal of Managerial Finance*, 14(4), 462-483.
- Ordue J.A., Yua H., Ityavyar D.V. & Tarnongo, T.J. (2024) Evaluating the Nexus between Macroeconomic Indicators and Stock Market Performance in Nigeria, *International Journal of Developing and Emerging Economies*, 12(1), 67-93
- Omale, E.A., **Yua, H.**, and Azubuike, P.E. (2024). Effect of Money Market Instruments on Banking Soundness in Nigeria, *Journal of Business and African Economy*, 10(2), 77-100
- Ozli, P. K. (2019). Determinants of banking stability in Nigeria. Online at <https://mpra.ub.uni-muenchen.de/94092/> MPRA Paper No. 94092,
- Salami, A. A. & Uthman, A. B. (2018). Bank capital, operating efficiency, and corporate performance in Nigeria. *Acta Univ. Sapientiae, Economics and Business*, 6 (2), 61–87.
- Sanusi, L. S. (2010). The Nigerian Banking Industry: What Went Wrong and the Way Forward. Convocation Lecture.

- Soomiyol, M., Bwuese, B. & Yua,H. (2023). Effect of Prudential Guidelines on the Financial Performance of Deposit Money Banksin Nigeria, *Journal of Global Accounting*, 9(4),118-146
- Sere-Ejembi, A., Udom, I. S., Salihu, A., Atoi, N. V., & Yaaba, B. N. (2014). Developing banking system stability index for Nigeria. *CBN Journal of Applied Statistics (JAS)*, 5(1), 49-77
- Teixeira, J. C., Matos, T. F., da Costa, G. L., & Fortuna, M. J. (2020). Investor protection, regulation and bank risk-taking behavior. *The North American Journal of Economics and Finance*, 51, 101051.
- Taherdoost, H. (2017). Determining sample size: How to calculate sample size, *International Journal of Economics and Management Systems*, 2, <https://ssm.com/abstract=3224205>
- Tochukwu, O. R. (2016) Capital adequacy and risk management: A study of the Nigerian banking sector, *International Journal of Innovative Science, Engineering &Technology*, 3(7), 342-354
- Uremadu, S. O., & Duru-Uremadu, C. E. (2018). A Review of Indices of Capital Adequacy and Performance among Nigerian Banks: A Theoretical Consideration. *Sumerianz Journal of Business Management and Marketing*, 1(1), 8-17.
- Yusuf, M. B. & Umar, A. I. (2021). Effect of bank capital regulation on stability of selected deposit money banks in Nigeria: A panel data approach. *Journal of Economics and Finance*, 12(2), 27-34.
- Yua, H., Ogohi, D.C. & Epor, S.O. (2022). Testing the Nexus between Financial Inclusion and Banks' Performance in Nigeria: The Role of Financial Technology. *World Scientific News*, 175(12), 37-52.
- Yua, H., Epor, S.O., & Utor V., (2023). The Sway of Financial Markets on Economic Growth: Evidence from Nigerian Stock Exchange, *Development Multidisciplinary international Journal* 7(1), 84 – 92
- Yua H., Ityavyar D.V & Yua, PM (2023). Interaction between Tax Administration and Tax Revenue Generation in Nigeria. *Development Multidisciplinary International Journal*, 7(1), 239-246
- Yua, H., Ogohi, D.C. & Epor, S.O. (2022). Testing the Nexus between Financial Inclusion and Banks' Performance in Nigeria: The Role of Financial Technology. *World Scientific News*, 175(12), 37-52.

Yua, H., Epor, S.O., & Ajekwe, (2025). Risk effects on bank stability measures in Nigeria:

Exploring the role of risk weighted, assets of selected deposit money banks in Nigeria. *International Journal of Business Systems and Economics*, 9(8), 89-105